

THE USE OF FERMENTATION OF CEREALS AND LEGUMES IN THE PRODUCTION OF FLOUR PRODUCTS**Vasyukova A.,***Professor, doctor of technical sciences,***Moshkin A.,***Technologist, candidate of technical sciences,***Talbi M.***Graduate student**Russian Biotechnology University***Abstract**

The development of a new line of products prepared using malts based on grains and legumes will allow solving the tasks set for the baking industry, saturating the market with enriched products with individual properties. The purpose of the work is to analyze the possibility of fermentation of grain crops to increase the nutritional value of raw materials and food products.

Materials and methods. The raw materials were: soft winter wheat «Moskovskaya 56», triticale of the «Nemchinovsky 56» variety, barley of the «Elf» variety, winter rye «Moskovskaya 12», «Nemchinovsky 50» - the plant variety "Pea sowing", the early ripe soybean variety «Kasatka». To determine the enzymatic activity of malt preparations, the samples were prepared according to a known method. The amylolytic activity of all obtained types of malt was determined colorimetrically on KFK-2 in dynamics under the influence of the pH environment, temperature, concentration of the substrate and enzyme.

Results and discussion. The activity of malt from rye, wheat, barley, soybeans, peas and triticale was studied in dynamics depending on various factors. It has been established that the maximum amylolytic activity of grain and legume malts is achieved at 40 °C. In the period from the beginning to the maximum activity, all samples showed a high rate of increase in activity, and in other time intervals, a gradual decrease in amylolytic activity was characteristic, and at 100 °C its value approached its initial state. These dynamics corresponds to the Van't Hoff rule. The beginning of enzyme denaturation in legumes has already been observed at 50°C, it is most pronounced at 80°C, and then rapidly decreases with an increase to 100°C. Thus, for wheat, the decrease was 20%, for rye - 25%, for triticale - 29.7%, and for barley - 44.4%. The data obtained are consistent with the results of scientists working in this field.

The study of the influence of the pH of the medium on the amylolytic activity of malt from grain and legume preparations showed that the maximum value of all preparations is observed at 5.5. A comparison of the results of the analyzes showed that the value of the enzymatic activity of triticale malt is 3.6 times greater than that of pea malt, which had the lowest enzymatic activity. The degree of ionization of ionogenic groups in the active center of triticale malt is higher than that of pea malt. There is an unequal affinity of the enzyme and the substrate, which means that different catalytic activity is observed. This is evidenced by the polynomial graphs of the dependence of the amylolytic activity of grain and legume malt preparations on the pH of the medium (with the maximum reliability of the approximation - $R^2 = 1$). Triticale malt has the highest enzymatic activity. Its activity is higher than that of wheat malt by 11.6-15.4%; rye - by 17.2-25.3%; barley variety "Elf" - by 29.0-31.0%, pea - by 62.1-65.3% and soybean - by 74.1% at an enzyme concentration of 1.0 and 3.0%. The obtained values are consistent with the scientific data of such researchers as Blinov A.A., Krol A.N., Kuntse V., Nazimova E.V., Narcis L., Shatko V.A.

To determine the Michaelis constant, graphical curves resembling a hyperbola were obtained. At a substrate concentration of 2.0%, the active centers of almost all enzyme preparations are filled. This can be seen in the slight change in reaction rate at a starch concentration of 2.0-3.0 g/dl, and the Michaelis constant, indicating a substrate concentration of half the maximum reaction rate. In this case, the Michaelis constant is in the range of 0.3-0.6 g/dl. The analysis of the obtained dependencies reveals the low amylolytic activity of legume malt. At a substrate concentration of 0.5 to 2.0 g/dl, the rate of catalysis of pea and soy malts increases by 9.8-22.4%, and at a concentration of 2.0 to 3.0 g/dl. respectively - by 5.4-7.4%. The values of the rate of amylolytic activity of grain malt are somewhat different. At a substrate (starch) concentration of 0.5 to 2.0 g/dl, the rate of catalysis of triticale malt increased by 26.5%, rye malt - by 20.1%, wheat malt - by 25.5%, barley malt - by 21.2%, and at a concentration of 2.0 to 3.0 g/dl. respectively - by 3.8; 11.4; 2.3; 1.0%. To enhance the extractivity of malt preparations, the appearance of the expected taste, unmalted materials can be added: rice chaff, barley flour, barley and corn defatted grits, soybeans, wheat, beet sugar and glucose (from 15 to 50% of the malt mass). It was found that the activity of malt from cereals at optimal pH and temperature was significantly higher than that of legumes. Triticale malt had the highest enzymatic activity.

Keywords: fermentation, malt, improvers, Amylolytic activity, cereals, food products.

Introduction

Grains of cereals, seeds of legumes and oilseeds are used to produce flour and up to 10% - for the production of malt and alcohol. Malt is a product made from germinated, dried and crushed grains: barley, wheat, rye, millet, oats, triticale, lentils, peas, buckwheat, rice and corn. It is used in many branches of the food industry. It is used in brewing, production of flour products, wine and alcohol-containing products (Vasyukova et al., 2005).

Fermented rye malt is known in baking for baking rye, rye-wheat, malt breads, where it is added in an amount of 3-5% by weight of flour. It is considered an effective flour improver, promotes better water absorption, improves dough elasticity, participates in the formation of the structure of the bread crumb, promotes the formation of soluble substances that enhance fermentation, provides longer storage of the finished product (Hu et al., 2004).

Malt is used in medicine, pharmaceuticals, alcohol, brewing, wine-making, baking and confectionery industries, for the production of baby food. In connection with the ever-growing demand for malt, an important technological task is to increase the yield of finished products from it, as well as to stimulate its amylolytic activity. To achieve this goal sulfonamides are currently used (Liflyandsky, 2004).

Non-fermented malt is used in baking as a natural saccharifying product, it is included in the recipe for gingerbread, bread and confectionery. White malt in the form of flour or malt extract is used in almost all types of European and American wheat dough (in addition to flour in the amount of 0.5-3% of its mass) (Hu et al., 2004).

Barley serves as a raw material for obtaining malt in brewing and distilling industries; rye is used to produce red malt. In addition, Kucherenko P.N. (2011) established a positive trend in the lengthening of the freshness of bread from the use of enzyme preparations. The process of hardening occurs 4 to 6 times slower. Nirciss L. (2007) showed that malt enriches food products with easily digestible proteins, carbohydrates, fiber, vitamins and minerals.

From the analysis of the literature, it follows that the enzymatic hydrolysis of starch is carried out using enzymes of the class of hydrolases, a subclass of carbohydrates called amylases: α -amylase, β -amylase and glucoamylase. They have been distinguished by their physical and chemical properties, distribution in nature and the way they act on starch grains. The amylases of sprouted grains have the highest activity. They hydrolyze both starch grains and starch paste.

Materials and methods

The raw materials were soft winter wheat «Moskovskaya 56», triticale variety «Nemchinovsky 56», barley variety "Elf", winter rye «Moskovskaya 12», «Nemchinovsky 50» – a plant variety "Pea sowing", an early ripe soybean variety in the Moscow region – «Kasatka».

Malt was made from grain and legume raw materials: Elf barley, wheat, rye, triticale, soybeans, peas (Moshkin et al., 2008; GOST (national standard) 20264-89). To determine the enzymatic activity of malt

preparations, the samples were prepared according to a known method. While 0.5 g of malt was dissolved in 50 ml of 1% NaCl solution and the resulting solution was filtered. The amylolytic activity of all obtained types of malt was determined calorimetrically in dynamics under the influence of the pH environment, temperature, concentration of the substrate and enzyme.

The amylolytic activity of all types of malt was determined by the formula proposed by Virovets O.A. and Zilova I.S. (2009)

$$X = \frac{(D - D_1)AV}{DHV_1}, \quad (1)$$

where D is the optical density of the control solution; D1 is the optical density of the test solution; H is the sample weight, g; A is the amount of added starch; V is the volume of the initial enzyme extract, ml; V1 is the volume of the extract taken for incubation, ml.

The quality of triticale fermented malt was determined by the method of Aleinikova T.L. and Rubtsova G.V. (1988). The values are shown in table 1. The quality of other types of malt (rye, wheat, pea, barley, soy) was determined according to the above method (Aleinikova, Rubtsova, 1988). The summarized results are given in tables 2, 3.

The obtained results allow us to judge that fermented triticale malt, as well as fermented and non-fermented rye malt in grains, met the requirements of GOST R 52061-2003 (Dry rye malt. Technical conditions).

The moisture content of wheat flour of the highest grade was determined according to the method described in the current regulatory documentation GOST 9404-88 (Flour and bran. Method for determination of moisture). According to this regulatory document, the quality of gluten was determined.

Determination of the titratable acidity of flour was carried out by titration of the water-flour mixture according to GOST 5670-96 (Bakery products. Methods for determination of acidity), dry weight in malt was determined - according to GOST 13586.5-2015 (Grain. Method for determination of moisture), protein and protein substances - according to GOST 10846-91 (Grain and products of its processing. Method for determination of protein).

The rheological properties of semi-finished products from premium wheat flour with the addition of malt were determined on a Brabender farinograph (GOST R 51404-99 (ISO 5530-1-97), Wheat flour).

The dynamic viscosity of the preparations was determined by the formula

$$\eta = M \cdot t \cdot K, \text{ mPa} \cdot \text{s}, \quad (2)$$

where M is the mass of the 2nd cylinder, g/cm²; t is the time of movement of the 2nd cylinder 30 mm, s; K is the constant of the 1st cylinder (0.1084).

The structural and mechanical properties of the dough were studied in terms of compressibility, relative plasticity and elasticity using an automated penetrometer AP-4/1 (Roiter, Demchuk, 1977).

The ash content of malt was determined according to GOST 10847-74 (Grain. Methods of ash content determination).

The redox potential was measured by the potentiometric method on a pH-meter in volts and rH₂ was calculated by the formula

$$rH2 = \frac{Eh}{0,029} + 2pH \quad (3)$$

Given that the formula includes pH, then rH2 gives a complete description of the redox state of the medium.

The content of solids in malt preparations was determined according to GOST 6687.2-86 (Products of soft drinks industry. Methods of determination of dry substances) by the areometric method, total titratable acidity - according to GOST 6687.4-86 (Soft drinks, kvass and syrups. Methods of determination of acidity), active acidity using a pH meter (Kovalskaya, 1991), and the mass fraction of dextrans by the method of M.P. Popova and E.F. Shanenko (Krakhmaleva, 2007). Reducing sugars were determined by the iodometric semi-micro method (Puchkova et al., 2005).

The evaluation of the structural and mechanical properties of the dough was determined by the indicators of compressibility, relative plasticity and elasticity, using an automated penetrometer AP-4/1 (Royter, Demchuk, 1977).

The number of yeast cells was determined on a Mikmed 5 microscope using the yeast cell count method (GOST R ISO 7218-2008 (Microbiology of food products and animal feed)).

The microbiological evaluation of preparations was carried out according to the method of I.A. Eremina (Eremina, Krieger, 2005). The actual humidity of the test - on the device VNIHP-VCh (Puchkova, 2004).

The density of the dough piece was found by calculation. The limiting shear stress of the test piece was obtained using the ST-1 structurometer by the general method.

To select malt preparations that have a greater influence on the formation of consumer properties, nutritional and biological value of bakery products, a study of consumer preferences was conducted. The purpose of the study was to identify the type of malt and the range of products most preferred by the respondents. As a quantified means of measurement, a point scale was chosen, which makes it possible to rank bread and bakery products, to evaluate them as average values of estimates. For analysis, the respondents recorded their age, gender, as well as weight and height characteristics for calculating the body mass index.

To study preferences, the following food groups were used: rye bread, rye-wheat, wheat, whole grain, bran, «Borodinsky» yeast-free, «Rizhsky», «Barsky», «Posolsky» bread using various malts; Butter buns, Viennese, diet.

To analyze the cause-and-effect relationships of the appearance of preferences, in addition to anthropometric data, adherence to a specific nutritional system was recorded: traditional, vegan, vegetarian, low-carbohydrate, low-protein, low-calorie, keto diet, protein, other (specify which one). Before completing the questionnaire, survey participants agreed to participate in the study and use personal data.

For the practical implementation of the survey, the module "Internet surveys" of the computer system "Monitoring of physical development and nutritional status" was used, the developed Internet questionnaire

was published on the profile page of the MSUTU website.

Mathematical modeling, statistical processing of research results, as well as solving the problem of optimizing the final proofing process were carried out on a PC using the Mathematica, MS Excel 2007 application software packages (2012).

During experimental studies, measurement errors were evaluated at all stages. The estimate corresponded to a confidence probability of $P = 0.95$. The measurement error did not exceed

0.4-1.0%. All direct and indirect measurements were carried out repeatedly in accordance with the measurement procedure on certified equipment.

Results and Discussion

Raw materials for malt production are available not only regionally, but also on a national scale. For example, according to FAO data for 2015, triticale is produced on an area of 3.6 million hectares. The largest sown areas (roma Russia and Ukraine) in Poland - more than 1.2 million hectares, Germany - 404 thousand hectares, France - 331 thousand hectares, Belarus - 376 thousand hectares. The average yield in 2006 in Germany was 55.9 dt/ha, in France - 51.2 dt/ha, Poland - 26.8, Belarus - 26 dt/ha. (M. M. Samim, J. Zhumashev, 2017).

According to the April USDA report, the area under wheat in the world was 221.96 million hectares and high average yield of 3.5 cwt/ha. The top five countries in terms of wheat planted area (million hectares) are: India, 31.4; Russia, 28.7 million hectares; China, 23.4 million hectares; U.S., 14.9 million hectares; and Australia, 13.0 million hectares. The world leaders in wheat yields in 2020/21 (t/ha) are: Germany, 7.53 t/ha; France, 6.8 t/ha; Egypt, 6.4; and China, 5.7 t/ha. The leaders in wheat production also remain the same. These are China, India and Russia. Only their total share decreased from 46% in 2019/20 MY to 42% in 2020/21 MY. Ukraine, which harvested 25.5 million tons of wheat, ranks 8th in the ranking of global producers (latifundist.com, 2021).

The leader in global rye production in 2018 was Germany, with 2.2 million tons of rye. Production in other countries was (million tons): Poland, 2.1; Russia, 1.9; China, 1.04; Belarus, 0.5; Denmark, 0.48; Ukraine, 0.39; Spain, 0.388; Turkey, 0.32; Canada, 0.236; USA, 0.214; Austria, 0.177; Czech Republic, 0.12; France, 0.11; UK, 0.095 (Direct.Farm, 2018).

Global barley production in 2014, according to the FAO, was 144.3 million tons. This was 0.3% less than in 2013. In 5 years (relative to 2009), global production of this cereal crop decreased by 4.9%, in 10 years (relative to 2004) by 6.2%, but there is a slight increase of 0.2% to 2001 figures (Agribusiness Expert Analysis Center, 2016).

The world leader in the production of green peas in 2016 was China, in second place - India, in third place - the United States. Captured (million tons): China, 12.2; India, 4.8; US, 0.31; France, 0.23; Egypt, 0.19; UK, 0.15; Pakistan, 0.149; Algeria, 0.13; Peru, 0.12; Turkey, 0.11; Russia, 0.1; Italy, 0.099; Hungary, 0.097; Spain, 0.087; Morocco, 0.076 (Rosstat, 2016).

The world leader in soybean production is the United States. Their total crop in 2018 was about 125 million tons - more than one-third of global soybean production. Global soybean production (million tons): Brazil, 115.34; Argentina, 54.20; China, 16.00; India, 12.50; Paraguay, 10.40; Canada, 7.51; Russia, 4.32; Ukraine, 4.01; EU countries, 3.29. (Direct.Farm, 2018).

Malt: extractivity, amylase activity, saccharifying ability

Currently, there are two fermented types of malt: white - active (mainly produced from barley) and red (from rye), inactive, undergone special processing - fermentation (Kurochkin et al., 2007).

The process of obtaining white and red malt consists of the same stages with one difference: to obtain red rye malt, the grains undergo additional temperature treatment - fermentation. In this case, the grains are languishing and drying in a special mode. It is thanks to this processing that the malt turns dark red with a specific taste (Krol, 2006).

The scheme for obtaining malt is reduced to germination, drying and grinding of grain. To obtain fermented malt, the technological process includes soaking, germination, fermentation, drying, grinding, storage.

Germination of cereals and legumes must be carried out at low temperatures. This is due to the optimal air temperature for the malting process in the range of 10 °C. In one room can be placed departments: for soaking grain, sprouting and languishing. The processes of drying, grinding and storage are carried out separately (Kosminsky, 1998).

At the first stage of malt production, its grain is prepared. The quality of the resulting malt depends on the feedstock. There are certain criteria must be met. So, for example, seeds must have at least 90% germination. Freshly harvested grain has little chance of germinating. The uniformity of sprout formation is ensured by the same grain size. The most suitable barley - 4- or 6-nuclear. Broken and weed grain is completely excluded (Kosminsky, 1998).

After the best grains for malting have been selected, they are soaked to obtain a moisture content ranging from 42 to 47%. Over the next week, the grains germinate. To obtain white malt, the grain is dried for 24 hours at a temperature not exceeding 50°C. This allows you to save the activity of the enzymes contained in the grain. To obtain red malt after the germination of grains, they are subjected to heating for 4 to 5 days. It can be self-heating or artificial heating of the grain mass is used. When the grain is heated to 55°C, the process of its fermentation takes place. During this period of the reaction between maltose, glucose and amino acids, polypeptides, the formation of melanoidins and various aroma-forming substances occur. They have a dark color, which makes the malt dark. Upon completion of the fermentation process, the grain is dried for 2 days. At the same time, the air temperature gradually increases to 70°C, the malt acquires a specific taste and aroma. Once the sprouts are removed, the malt is ground. Then it is screened and packed (Balashov, Rudolf, 1981).

According to the same scheme, malt is obtained from rye, oats and barley. The process of obtaining millet malt is somewhat complicated. It should be noted that even a very small proportion of millet malt allows you to get a very strong starter.

The method for the production of malt from lentils, developed by V.A. Blinov and A.A. Shatko (2011), includes grain cleaning and sorting. Soaking is carried out with the introduction of additives, alternating soaking at a temperature of 10 to 16°C for 2 to 4 hours, and infusion without water for 12 to 14 hours, malting, drying fresh malt, freeing malt from sprouts. As an additive, a solution of colloidal gold with a concentration of 0.00325 nmol/l is added to the key water before soaking the grains of lentils, with the following ratio of components, wt.%: a solution of colloidal gold with a concentration of 0.00325 nmol/l - 10%; water - 90%. This allows you to increase the enzymatic activity and energy of germination of lentil grains, as well as reduce the time for obtaining finished malt and, as a result, expand the scope of malt from lentils (Kobelev et al., 2013).

The preparation of buckwheat malt, as noted by Tanashkina T.V., Trotsenko A.S. and Korchagin V.P. (2014), has its distinctive features. The malting process is carried out by water irrigation of buckwheat grain at a temperature of (15 ± 1) °C for 72 to 75 hours, and drying is carried out at an airflow rate of 0.7 to 0.9 m/s in two stages, first from 5 to 6 h at a temperature of (50 ± 3) °C, and then from 5 to 6 h at a temperature of (60 ± 3) °C. This allows to reduce the time of the process of obtaining buckwheat malt, with low losses of solids, and high physical and chemical parameters, which ensures its enzymatic activity.

Buckwheat malt - can be used in the alcohol industry, in the production of gluten-free beer of top and bottom fermentation, non-alcoholic beer, kvass, poly-malt preparations, in the baking industry. This type of malt gives the products a special, nut-malty taste and aroma (Balashov, Rudolf, 1981; Starkova, 2014).

In recent years, malt has been obtained from corn grain. It is distinguished by good extractivity, contains a large amount of α -amylase, similar in nature of action to barley malt α -amylase. However, its saccharifying ability is 16 to 30 times less than that of barley malt. Moreover, corn malt amylase is more resistant to high temperatures than barley malt. In addition to grain crops, legumes are also raw materials for the production of malt. Legumes include chickpeas, mung or mung beans, soybeans, peanuts, lentils, beans, peas and beans. Legumes contain protein, mainly in a particularly valuable form - in the form of legumin. In addition, legume protein contains essential amino acids: lysine, tryptophan, histidine, methionine. According to the content of easily digestible proteins, they have no equal among vegetable plants. They are also rich in pectin, sugars, vitamins A, B, ascorbic acid, starch and other nutrients (Trautenberg, 1985; Toshev, 2002; Marchik, Efremov, 2006; Zotikov, Sidorenko, 2017).

Peas and soybeans differ from other grains in their high protein content. In the process of malting, under the action of proteolytic enzymes, protein substances, including essential amino acids, accumulate in the grains of legumes (Marchik, Efremov, 2006).

Both sprouted and unsprouted legumes are valuable additives in the production of polymalt extracts, high-protein drinks and baby food (Tertychnaya, Manzhesov et al., 2010).

Malt obtained from legumes differs from cereals in greater enzymatic activity. In addition to barley-malt extract, corn-malt extract has been produced some years or several years and in recent years, polymalt extracts have become widespread, which are prepared from a mixture of malts from several kinds of cereal (Tertychnaya et al., 2010).

Multi-enzyme product from legumes, i.e. sprouted peas is a product consisting of highly active plant hydrolases used for saccharification of grain feed (Emelyanova et al., 2014). Pea malt can compete with most bacterial and fungal enzyme preparations tested on the market. Pea germination can be organized in any farm, the cost of pea malt is an order of magnitude lower than the cost of enzyme preparations, sold on the market. It does not require special equipment for its production. In table 4 presents comparative data on polysaccharides activity (sum of mono- and disaccharides, mg/min/g) (Belokurova et al., 2012).

As can be seen from Table 4, the total polysaccharides activity of pea malt exceeds that of barley malt by 115%, rye malt - by 113%, MEK CX-2 - by 61%. Plant hydrolases of pea malt can be effectively used for the enzymatic treatment of grain feed. The enzyme product has a wide range of amylase, pullulanase, glycosidase, fructofuranosidase, cellulase, hemicellulase, xylanase, pectinase, protease, lipase, phosphatase activity (Belokurova et al., 2012).

Thus, pea malt has the lowest extractivity and wheat malt has the highest. Corn malt has the lowest amylase activity. Therefore, it must be processed in a mixture with wheat and oatmeal, which has a higher saccharifying ability (Tertychnaya et al., 2010).

Characteristics of different types of malts and their enzymatic activity

At the beginning of the 19th century, for the first time, Russian scientists established the possibility of saccharifying starch with an extract from germinated barley (Bityukov et al., 2008). The resulting malt liquefies and saccharifies starch in the presence of acids and elevated temperatures. However, extracts act ambiguously. With an increase in temperature, the saccharifying ability of malt decreases, and the acidity liquefies the starch. It has been established that malt consists of two components. The temperature optimum for barley extract action is in the range from 45 to 50°C, and for barley malt from 50 to 55°C. The extract from barley under the specified parameters destroys starch grains (Simakova et al., 1996).

Russian scientists have made significant progress in the study of malt enzymes and the mechanism of their action on the starch molecule. Moreover, α -amylase breaks down the molecules of amylose and amylopectin into separate high-molecular components called dextrans. It has been experimentally proven that α -amylase has the ability to break α -1,4 glucosidic bonds anywhere in starch chains. As a result of the influence of α -amylase, the concentration of reducing substances decreases and the paste is destroyed. And β -

amylase at this time saccharifies amylose and dextrans formed during the hydrolysis of starch. Moreover, amylopectin is saccharified by β -amylase to maltose and dextrans in a ratio of 54 and 46%. In addition, it was found that β -amylase breaks bonds only in the branches of the amylopectin molecule and this process stops at the branching points (Kuznetsov, 1964).

Klimovsky D.N. and Rodzevich V.I. (1951), engaged in the enzymatic cleavage of starch, found that the cleavage of amylopectin leaves phosphodextrans that cannot be saccharified by α - and β -amylases. For the saccharification of phosphodextrans to occur, their bond with phosphoric acid must first be broken.

Yarovenko V.L., Kalunyants K.A. and Gloter L.I. (1991, 1992) found that for the complete saccharification of starch, in addition to α - and β -amylase, a third enzyme is also needed - dextrinophosphatase, called dextrinase for short. This new enzyme completes the hydrolysis process. The essence of the enzymatic hydrolysis of starch under the influence of enzymes is the action of α - and β -amylase on amylose (amylolytic ability), and dextrinophosphatase on amylopectin (dextrinolytic ability). Amylolytic ability is determined by the amount of dextrans that are not stained with iodine, obtained by hydrolysis of starch in 1 hour at 30 ° under the action of malt. Dextrinolytic ability can be measured by the number of milligrams of phosphodextrans saccharified to maltose by 1 gram of malt for 1 hour at 30°C. In addition, the same scientists studied the amylolytic ability and dextrinolytic ability of green malt of various origins.

For a more complete saccharification of starch contained in raw materials, it has been found that it is advisable to create mixtures from various malts - barley, millet and oat, which has long been practiced in production (Sharova, 2006).

In Russia, under GOST 29294-92 (Barley malt. Technical conditions), the following types of malt are distinguished according to the method of preparation: light, dark, caramel and burnt.

A number of studies have revealed the effect of temperature, acidity, pH on the saccharification process and on the activity of malt enzymes (Ginzburg, 1955; Goryacheva, Kuzminsky, 1983; Vasyukova et al., 2015). The malt of different cereals contains different amounts of enzymes (Table 5).

With a decrease in the duration of exposure to temperature to 30 minutes, as experiments have shown, this loss is reduced by only 7% (Table 6). Therefore, the temperature affects amylase to a much greater extent than the duration of exposure (Sharova, 2006; Bityukov et al., 2008).

Academician A.I. Oparin established that the reason for the inactivation of amylase during heating of malt extracts is the coagulation of proteins, which, in this case, partially or completely adsorb the enzyme from the solution. Since amylases are enzymes of the hydrolase class, they catalyze the hydrolysis of starch, glycogen, and other related oligo- and polysaccharides. Amylases are a combination of two enzymes: α - and β -amylases (Oparin, 1938; Glazunov, 1938; Kizima, 1946; Kozmina and Kretovich, 1951; Kozmina, 1971;

Aistova and Pleshkov, 1975). A.I. Oparin and N.N. Dyachkov (1928), A. Kursanov and K. Bryushkova (1940) note that α -amylases hydrolyze α -1,4 bonds within the starch molecule, breaking the bond between the first carbon atom and oxygen binding this carbon to the neighboring glucose molecule (Oparin, Dyachkov, 1928).

Recent studies in the field of amylases have shown that maturation α -amylase and germination α -amylase are present in plant seeds (Trautenberg and Vitol, 2007). If the medium in which the amylase is located contains sugar or peptone, then they prevent the coagulation of proteins at high temperatures and thereby protect the amylase from inactivation. The experimental data of A.I. Oparin and S.M. Manskaya (1928) proved that protein coagulation decreases with increasing sugar concentration.

Due to this, when heated, the activity of amylase is better preserved (Machikhina et al., 2005). This explains the protective effect of carbohydrates against amylase. Since boiled mass and sweet mash contain starch, dextrins and sugars, the high temperature here is less dangerous for amylase than in aqueous solutions.

According to the studies of many authors, it has been established that the optimal pH zone for the action of amylase is in the range from 4.7 to 5.1. When studying the influence of pH separately for α - and β -amylase, it was found that for α -amylase the optimum is approximately 6.0, and for β -amylase - 4.8. The inactivating effect of pH increases with increasing temperature. At pH below 2.3 and above 9.7 amylase completely stops its action.

According to Oparin A.I. and Dyachkov N.N. (1928), the inactivation of amylase by acidity can be prevented by adding peptone to the medium. But this applies only to the pH zone in the range from 3.5 to 6.2. Outside this range, the addition of peptone cannot protect the amylase from acid inactivation. The natural acidity of sweet congestion from different types of raw materials ranges from 0.15 to 0.30, which on average corresponds to a pH of 5.2 to 5.6. This acidity is favorable for the thinning action of amylase, for which at 65° the optimum pH is from 5.4 to 5.8. In wet years with low temperatures, the grain has a higher enzymatic and diastatic activity.

A semi-continuous technological scheme of saccharification in two stages was studied. At the first stage, 10% of the total intended amount of malted milk was added to the boiled mass and the temperature was maintained from 68 to 70°C for 10 minutes. At the second stage, the rest of the malt was added and saccharification took place at a temperature of 59 to 60°C for 10 and 2 minutes. (Sharova, 2006).

Ashkinuzi Z.K. and Raev Z.A. (2022), compared the process of saccharification from 55 to 56°C for 20 minutes, and then for 10 minutes at 60°C. It was found that in sweet mashes saccharified by the two-stage method, the activity of malt amylolytic enzymes was better preserved. Therefore, the method also obtained a higher yield of alcohol. However, the degree of starch saccharification, as well as the ratio of maltose and dextrins, were inferior to the control data. Thus, it was found that two-stage saccharification does not provide

the desired efficiency of enzymatic cleavage starch, compared with the periodic scheme. Therefore, the main indicator for assessing the quality of mash should be considered its saccharifying ability.

To find out the effect of reducing the saccharification time on the microflora of sweet congestion, scientists such as Klimovsky D.N. and Rodzevich V.I. (1951), Kalunyants K.A. (1990; 1992), the degree of their sterility was checked by the method of self-fermentation by increasing acidity after 48 hours of fermentation. Saccharification was carried out with non-antiseptic and antiseptic malted milk. It has been established that the degree of sterility is primarily determined by temperature, which can be seen from a comparison of three modes of a single-stage saccharification method. With the same duration of the process, only the temperature changed.

When comparing Klimovsky D.N. of the modes of the two-stage saccharification method, the effect of the duration of the process on the sterility of the mash was established. This is also confirmed by subsequent studies by Klimovsky D.N. and Rodzevich V.I. on the role of dextrinase in the saccharification of terminal dextrins.

Thus, it has been established that amylases catalyze the hydrolysis of starch, glycogen, and polysaccharides. To activate the process of saccharification of carbohydrates (starch), it is advisable to use mixtures of various malts - barley, millet and oat.

Development of a new line of products prepared with the use of malts based on cereals and legumes will allow to solve the challenges of the baking industry, saturate the market with enriched bakery products with individual distinctive properties: improved taste and flavor, which meet the requirements for high-quality bakery products and meet the needs of buyers, taking into account their preferences.

The Michaelis constant and the dependence of the reaction rate on the concentration of the substrate

We have studied the dynamics of the activity of malt from rye, wheat, Elf barley, soybeans, peas and triticale depending on different concentrations of the substrate (Moshkin et al., 2014). Thus, two most important characteristics were obtained - this is the Michaelis constant and the dependence of the reaction rate on the concentration of the substrate, described by the equation proposed by him:

$$v = \frac{v_{\max} [S]}{K_m + [S]}, \quad (4)$$

where: v is the reaction rate, units/s; v_{\max} is the maximum reaction rate, units; S - substrate concentration, g/dl; K is the Michaelis constant, g/dl.

The change in the enzymatic activity of malt from rye, wheat, Elf barley, soybeans, peas and triticale is shown in fig. 1. It has been established that the maximum amylolytic activity of grain and legume malts is achieved at 40 °C. In the period from the beginning to the maximum activity, all samples showed a high rate of increase in activity, and in other time intervals, a gradual decrease in amylolytic activity was characteristic, and at 100 °C its value approached its initial state. This dynamics corresponds to the Van't Hoff rule.

At the same time, this temperature interval was not noted for legumes. The increase in the rate of amylolytic activity for legumes was: for peas - 22.5; 49.6; 37.4; 34.8; 33.84%, and for soybeans - 26.7; 45.0; 42.2; 40.9; 8.4%. The onset of enzyme denaturation in legumes was already observed at 50°C and then slowly decreased to 100°C. Experiments have shown that the denaturation of grain crop enzymes is most pronounced at 80°C, and then rapidly decreases as the temperature rises to 100°C. Thus, for wheat, the decrease was 20%, for rye - 25%, for triticale - 29.7% and for barley - 44.4%.

Soybean and pea enzymatic activity curves were flatter than those for cereals. The loss of activity of pea enzymes at 80 °C was 34.74% and soybean - 40.07%. At 100 °C, it decreased even more, but was detectable.

Thus, the increase and decrease in the amylolytic activity of legume and grain malt preparations differ significantly. The data obtained are consistent with the results of scientists working in this field.

The study of the influence of the medium pH on the amylolytic activity of malt from grain and legume preparations showed that the maximum value of all preparations is observed at 5.5, which is shown in fig. 2.

It was found that the maximum amylolytic activity was observed in triticale malt at pH 5.5. Moreover, it was found that the increase and decrease in amylolytic activity in all samples occurs identically. Comparison of the results of the analyzes showed that the value of the enzymatic activity of triticale malt is 3.6 times greater than that of pea malt, which had the lowest enzymatic activity. The activity of soy malt is quite close to the latter.

The nature of the change in the amylolytic activity of various malt preparations depending on the pH of the medium was described by the following equations:

$$\text{- triticale malt: } y = -1,146x^2 + 119,97x + 686,79; R^2 = 0,9202;$$

$$\text{- wheat malt: } y = -1,8348x^2 + 190,7x + 767,86; R^2 = 0,9479;$$

$$\text{- rye malt: } y = -1,3862x^2 + 144,97x + 708,93; R^2 = 0,9298;$$

$$\text{- barley malt: } y = -0,4893x^2 + 52,51x + 700; R^2 = 0,9845;$$

$$\text{- soy malt: } y = -0,0835x^2 + 11,591x - 648,21; R^2 = 0,8725;$$

$$\text{- pea malt: } y = -0,0804x^2 + 11,179x - 635,71; R^2 = 0,9687.$$

$$F_{\text{ras}} = \text{dis1/dis2}; F_{\text{tab}}(0.05,5,4) = 6.26$$

$F_{\text{ras}} > F_{\text{tab}}(0.05,5,4)$, hence the regression equation is significant.

The experimental data obtained on their basis allow us to consider that the degree of ionization of ionogenic groups in the active center of triticale malt is higher than that of pea malt. This allows us to conclude that there is an unequal affinity of the enzyme and substrate, which means different catalytic activity is observed. This is evidenced by the polynomial graphs of the dependence of the amylolytic activity of grain and legume malt preparations on the medium pH (with the maximum reliability of the approximation – $R^2 = 1$).

In addition, the dependence of the amylolytic activity of grain and legume malts on the concentration of the enzyme preparation was clarified. The results of these experiments are presented in fig. 3.

Moreover, it was found that malts of grain crops have the greatest amylolytic activity.

The change in the amylolytic activity of grain and legume malts depending on the concentration of the enzyme preparation can be described by the following equations:

$$\text{- triticale malt: } y = 841,61x^{1,194} - \text{power}; R^2 = 0,9963;$$

$$\text{- wheat malt: } y = 3079,2 \ln(x) + 140,19 - \text{logarithmic}; R^2 = 0,9678;$$

$$\text{- rye malt: } y = 16,667x^5 - 283,33x^4 + 1695,8x^3 - 4716,7x^2 + 7186,7x - 3600 - \text{polynomial}; R^2 = 1;$$

$$\text{- barley malt: } y = 17,5x^5 - 708,33x^3 - 2237,5x^2 + 1091,7x - 3608 - \text{polynomial}; R^2 = 1;$$

$$\text{- soy malt: } y = 25,926x^3 - 290,08x^2 + 1398,3x - 953,33 - \text{polynomial}; R^2 = 0,999;$$

$$\text{- pea malt: } y = 334,29x - 186,67 - \text{linear}; R^2 = 0,9935.$$

The results of experiments on the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes at different concentrations of the enzyme (Table 7). Given in table data show that triticale malt has the highest enzymatic activity. Its activity is higher than that of wheat malt by 11.6-15.4%; rye - by 17.2-25.3%; barley variety "Elf" - by 29.0-31.0%, pea - by 62.1-65.3% and soybean - by 74.1% at an enzyme concentration of 1.0 and 3.0%.

The results of studies of various concentrations of the substrate on the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes are given in table 8. The obtained results show that the longest saturation of the active center of the enzyme with the substrate is observed in triticale malt. The obtained values are consistent with the scientific data of such researchers as Blinov (2011), Krol (2006), Kuntze, Nazimova (2017), Narcis (2007).

To determine the Michaelis constant, graphic curves were obtained showing the effect of various concentrations of the enzyme on the amylolytic activity of malt from cereals and legumes (fig. 4).

From fig. 4 shows that the curves of grain crops resemble a hyperbole. At a substrate concentration of 2.0%, the active centers of almost all enzyme preparations are filled. This can be seen in the slight change in reaction rate at a starch concentration of 2.0-3.0 g/dl and the Michaelis constant, indicating a substrate concentration of half the maximum reaction rate.

In this case, the Michaelis constant is in the range of 0.3-0.6 g/dl. In accordance with the equation of the reaction rate from the concentration of the substrate, described by the Michaelis-Menten equation:

$$v \text{ triticale malt} - 2.76 \text{ units/s}; v \text{ wheat malt} - 2.28 \text{ units/s};$$

$$v \text{ barley malt} - 1.89 \text{ units/s}; v \text{ rye malt} - 1.94 \text{ units/s};$$

$$v \text{ of pea malt} - 0.74 \text{ units/s}; v \text{ soy malt} - 0.51 \text{ units/s}.$$

The analysis of the dependences obtained (Fig. 4) reveals the low amylolytic activity of legume malt. At a substrate concentration of 0.5 to 2.0 g/dl. the rate of catalysis of pea and soy malts increases by 9.8 - 22.4%,

and at a concentration of 2.0 to 3.0 g/dl. respectively - by 5.4 - 7.4%.

The values of the rate of amylolytic activity of grain malt are somewhat different. At a substrate (starch) concentration of 0.5 to 2.0 g/dl. the rate of catalysis of triticale malt increased by 26.5%, rye malt - by 20.1%, wheat malt - by 25.5%, barley malt - by 21.2%, and at a concentration of 2.0 to 3.0 g/dl respectively - by 3.8; 11.4; 2.3; 1.0%.

To enhance the extractivity of malt preparations, the appearance of the expected taste, unmalted materials can be added: rice chaff, barley flour, barley and defatted corn grits, soybeans, possibly also wheat, hulled barley, beet sugar and glucose. The total amount of added unmalted materials usually ranges from 15 to 50% of the mass of malt (Akzhigitova, 2011, Tertychnaya et al., 2010, Bertinet, 2010).

Thus, as a result of the studies of the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes, it was found that their amylolytic activity differs and depends on the type of crop. The activity of malt from cereals at optimal pH and temperature was significantly higher than that of legumes. Triticale malt had the maximum enzymatic activity. Triticale malt had the highest rate of enzymatic reaction depending on the substrate concentration.

However, it is necessary to find out the quality of the malt and its dependence on the degree of its dissolution during the germination process. Therefore, we will consider the relationship between individual indicators of barley and malt, since during the germination of grain, endo- β -glucanases are synthesized in the cells of the aleurone layer. They penetrate into the endosperm and destroy the glucan that enters the cell walls of endosperm cells (Kuznetsova et al., 2013). Since the activity of the enzyme decreases sharply during drying, its action is mainly limited to malting; exo- β -glucanases that cleave di- and trisaccharides from the reducing ends of the β -glucan. These enzymes are produced mainly by the shield in the presence of calcium ions and gibberellic acid. In this regard, further research on the hydrolysis of flour starch is carried out in conjunction with calcium ions, which will activate enzymes from cereals and legumes.

Given the high amylolytic activity of triticale malt compared to barley, we studied the amylolytic activity of these preparations obtained as a result of two-day germination and careful drying, when exposed to calcium ions.

As substrates for the detection of amylolytic activity of malts, wheat flour of the highest grade was used; a solution of 2% dextrinized starch, as well as dry potato starch. Fixed with a solution of the reaction mixture of maltose. A 5% aqueous extract was prepared from triticale malt, which was used as an enzyme. The results obtained were compared with the studies of Tsyperovich A.S.

Back in 1971, Tsyperovich A.S. (2005) showed the benefits of enzyme action on native and gelatinized starch. The effect of amylases is very small on whole or partially damaged starch grains. Therefore, studies of the interaction of native and dextrinized starch with various enzyme preparations activated by calcium ions

from triticale and barley malts made it possible to reveal their enzymatic activity (table).

Judging by these data, the amylase complex of triticale malt is no less active than barley malt, both in dry form and in the form of an extract. The experiment to assess the amylase activity of non-germinated triticale seeds confirms the well-known fact of an increase in enzyme activity in germinating grain (Kretovich, 1980; Tertychnaya et al., 2010; Emelyanova et al., 2014).

However, the activity of triticale malt can be increased with small additions of Ca^{2+} ions. Indeed, a small addition of a calcium chloride solution with a concentration of Ca^{2+} ions of 0.5 g/l increases the amylase activity of the drug and brings it to a higher level than that of barley malt.

A similar picture is also preserved when the enzyme extract is prepared not with distilled water, but with a solution of calcium chloride with a concentration of calcium ions of 0.01 g/l. At the same time, the concentration of calcium ions in the saccharified solution is an order of magnitude lower than in the previous case and the saccharifying activity of the drug even slightly increases.

The explanation for this should be sought, most likely, in the method of preparing the enzyme extract - when using an electrolyte solution, a more complete extraction of the enzyme from the raw material occurs, as is typical for many proteins and an increase in its concentration in the saccharified solution (Sidorenko, 2013).

The results obtained gave grounds to conduct studies of the amylolytic activity of triticale malt on wheat flour, the data of which are given in table 9. The patterns described above are completely preserved. As follows from the data obtained the sugar-forming ability of flour increases with the addition of dry triticale malt. When the reaction is carried out using not distilled, but tap water, the activity of amylases increases even more, which confirms the effect of calcium ions, which activate the action of amylolytic enzymes of grain malts.

The introduction of grain and legume malt preparations leads to the intensification of the process of preparing dough from wheat flour of the highest grade - dough preparation time is reduced by reducing the duration of fermentation on average by 1.5 - 2 times, depending on the dosage and type of malt introduced.

After mathematical processing of technological processes of dough-making with the use of yeast and malt preparations (1-3%) from grain and leguminous raw materials the equations were obtained:

- with rye malt: $y = 0,0643x^2 + 0,3443x + 8$ - polynomial; $R^2 = 0.9954$;

- with triticale malt: $y = 0,0833x^3 - 1,5357x^2 + 7,881x - 0,5$ - polynomial; $R^2 = 0.9848$;

- with wheat malt: $y = 5,3469\ln(x) + 6,5803$ - logarithmic; $R^2 = 0.9662$;

- with pea malt: $y = 7,3157\ln(x) + 5,5952$ - logarithmic; $R^2 = 0.9693$;

- with barley malt: $y = 1,375x^4 - 16,083x^3 + 63,625x^2 - 96,917x + 57$ - polynomial; $R^2 = 1$;

- with soy malt: $y = 0,1667x^4 - 2,1667x^3 + 9,333x^2 - 12,833x + 10,6$ - polynomial; $R^2 = 1$,

where R^2 is the value of approximation reliability.

Thus, in accordance with the methodology of baking technology established that the most intense process of dough processing is observed at 3% concentration of malt.

Table 1 - Evaluation of the quality of triticale malt

Table 2 - Physical and chemical indicators of malt

Table 3 - Estimates of quality indicators of the studied malts

Table 4 - Polysaccharides activity of various malts

Table 5 - Enzymatic activity of grain crops

Table 6 - Effect of temperature on enzymatic activity amylase

Table 7 - Enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes depending on the concentration of the enzyme

Table 8 - Enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes depending on the concentration of the substrate

Table 9 - Hydrolysis of starch under the action of malt amylases

Figure 1 - Change in the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes

Figure 2 - The influence of the medium pH on the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes

Figure 3 - Effect of different enzyme concentrations on the enzymatic activity of malt from cereals and legumes

Figure 4 - Effect of enzyme concentrations on the amyolytic activity of malt from cereals and legumes

Conclusion

Thus, the data obtained allow us to state that triticale malt, activated by calcium ions, even in minimal concentrations, exhibits increased amylase activity. Therefore, when using malts in dough preparation, there is no need to soften the water. In the technological process, drinking water supplied to the enterprise through the water supply system can be used.

A similar picture is also preserved when the enzyme extract is prepared not with distilled water, but with a solution of calcium chloride with a concentration of calcium ions of 0.01 g/l. At the same time, the concentration of calcium ions in the saccharified solution is an order of magnitude lower than in the previous case

and the saccharifying activity of the drug even slightly increases.

The explanation for this should be sought, most likely, in the method of preparing the enzyme extract - when using an electrolyte solution, a more complete extraction of the enzyme from the raw material occurs, as is typical for many proteins, and an increase in its concentration in the saccharified solution (Sidorenko, 2013; Vasyukova et al., 2015).

In conclusion, it should be noted separately the prospects for the development of this direction of research in both the nutrition, food industry and the agro-industrial complex. The totality of comparable data is

confirmed by the accumulated experience and a number of modern professional publications in some of the world's leading publications (Adebo et al., 2022; Caponio et al., 2022; Li et al., 2022; Skowron et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022).

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